

An EOSC-enabled Data Space Environment for Climate Science

Donatello Elia^{1*}, Sandro Fiore², Fabrizio Antonio¹, Guillaume Levavasseur³,
Paola Nassisi¹, Alessandro D’Anca¹, Sylvie Joussaume³, Giovanni Aloisio^{1,4}

¹Advanced Scientific Computing Division, Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, Lecce, Italy

²Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, University of Trento, Trento, Italy

³Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL), Centre National de Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), France

⁴Department of Innovation Engineering, University of Salento, Italy

Abstract—In the context of the European Open Science Cloud, the ENES Data Space represents a domain-specific implementation of the data space concept, a digital ecosystem supporting scientific communities towards a more sustainable, effective, and FAIR use of data. Such ecosystem has been recently opened to climate users, offering datasets, tools, and services into a single environment with ready-to-use data and programmatic capabilities for the development of data science applications. Presently, the data store of the ENES Data Space provides access to models output from large-scale global experiments for climate model intercomparison. The storage and computational resources for the execution of the data space are provided by the EGI Federated Cloud e-Infrastructure. From a science gateway perspective, the ENES Data Space provides an interactive web-based environment based on the Jupyter project and available through the EOSC Marketplace.

Keywords—Data Space, Climate Science, Open Science

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade big data has been considered one of the major revolutions in ICT. Besides the most famous three Vs, i.e., volume, velocity, and variety [1], a fourth one, value, at the core of data economy, has been fostering a data-driven innovation perspective, approach, and thinking, thus gaining strategic importance in the digital market, both for public and private sectors.

The data space concept has been progressively introduced in this context over the last few years, turning out to be very attractive and suitable also to scientific domains. In 2018, a common *European data space* was defined as a seamless digital area with a scale that will enable the development of new products and services based on data [2]. On the same line, a couple of years later, the *EU Data Strategy* [3] reported that the EU should create an attractive policy environment with the aim of defining a single European data space. Such space would represent a genuine single market for data, open to data from across the world, with investments in tools, standards, and infrastructure as well as proper efforts at the level of legislation and governance frameworks.

In that respect, the ongoing efforts in the context of the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC) [4], [5] can strongly help the implementation of such concept in several contexts.

As an example, the *EGI-ACE* project¹ is building several data spaces for different scientific communities to support them towards a more sustainable, effective, and FAIR data use [6].

Among others, the *ENES Data Space* is a notable example, relevant to the *European Network for Earth System Modelling* (ENES) community. It has been recently opened to the end users, offering data, tools, and services into a single environment with ready-to-use data and programmatic capabilities for the development of data science applications. In particular, this solution integrates into a single environment: (i) Python libraries and frameworks for data analytics and visualisation, together with (ii) a large data collection from key community experiments, like the *Coupled Model Intercomparison Project* (CMIP) [7] and (iii) scalable computing resources that can be deployed on demand on top of the *EGI federated cloud* infrastructure.

The ENES Data Space exploits software components from the *Jupyter project* [8] to provide a web-based and graphical entry point to the virtual research environment, available through the EOSC Marketplace in the context of the EOSC initiative². Such environment is at the core of this paper and will be presented in detail in the next sections.

The rest of the article is organized as it follows. Section II introduces the scientific context for the ENES Data Space as well as its role with respect to the legacy federated data distribution network. Section III introduces the software architecture requirements and some implementation details about the components used. Then, Section IV describes some real scientific applications targeted by the platform, while Section V introduces some similar efforts from literature. Finally, Section VI draws the conclusions and presents some key aspects worth of investigation for future works.

II. A DATA SPACE FOR CLIMATE SCIENCE

The increased models resolution in the development of comprehensive Earth System Models is rapidly leading to very large climate simulations outputs that pose significant challenges in terms of scientific data management, specifically for

¹EGI-ACE project: <https://www.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/>

²ENES Data Space on the EOSC Portal: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/enes-data-space>

* Corresponding author email: donatello.elia@cmcc.it

data sharing, processing, analysis, visualization, preservation, curation, and archiving [9], [10].

In such domain, large scale global experiments for climate model intercomparison (CMIP*) have led to the development of the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF [11]), a federated data infrastructure that involves a large set of modelling centres (data providers) around the globe and includes the European contribution - regarding the ENES community - through the IS-ENES project. Datasets are produced by the different climate modelling institutes, published on their sites, and shared with the whole community through ESGF.

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) has been established by the Working Group on Coupled Modelling [12] (WGCM) under the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP). CMIP is now in Phase 6 (CMIP6) and its PB-scale database [13], [14] is of strong relevance to WCRP for the IPCC assessments³.

A data space for climate and ESGF would be clearly linked in this landscape, due to the comprehensive data offering from ESGF about datasets of broad interest, from large community experiments.

From an architectural perspective, a climate data space and ESGF would work at two different levels:

- 1) ESGF would mainly operate a federated data archive through a set of data nodes distributed worldwide across different modelling centers;
- 2) a climate data space would provide a single entry-point to compute capabilities co-located with a local data store hosting a specific data selection from ESGF.

As already mentioned, the data offering is at the core of a climate data space. However, it is important to remark that data alone would not be enough without a comprehensive data space ecosystem, which also includes a potentially wide set of tools and services enabling scientists to: develop applications, analyze data, visualize results, understand provenance, reproduce analyses, share code and document workflows, publish new products etc. Data, services, and tools represent the three fundamental components of a climate data space ecosystem.

III. THE ENES DATA SPACE

This section provides an in-depth description of the ENES Data Space, which is a specific implementation of a climate data space developed in the context of the EU-funded project EGI-ACE. Specifically, the following three subsections highlight, respectively, the key objectives, the architecture and its implementation.

A. ENES Data Space Key Objectives

The ENES Data Space aims to provide a complete data science environment enabling users to perform scientific data analysis on climate datasets. It integrates computing and storage resources, climate datasets as well as various data access, analytics and visualization services, tools, and frameworks.

The ENES Data Space targets a set of key requirements, including among the most relevant ones:

- *Usability and productivity*: the typical methodology used by scientists consisted in downloading the datasets on their desktop machines and then processing data locally with home-made scripts. The increasing volumes of data has caused a deep transformation in several scientific domains, which made this approach no longer viable as it takes too long to download the data and set up the software needed to handle these complex datasets. It is, thus, of paramount importance to provide scientists with ready-to-use datasets and software solutions which can eliminate the setup time and increase their productivity;
- *Interactive and exploratory analysis*: data exploration represents one of the most common methodologies used by scientists for investigating and analyzing data. Providing tools able to effectively access, process and visualize data in an interactive manner is thus a key requirement for the software environment;
- *Parallel processing*: as the volumes of data continue to grow, support for parallel execution of the analysis is another fundamental aspect that must be considered. In this respect, modern High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) frameworks can easily allow scaling the analysis on thousands of computing units;
- *Scalable infrastructure*: it is important to provide scalable infrastructural services (i.e., cloud-based) to enable on-demand deployment of applications of different complexities and under heterogeneous workloads;
- *Research outputs sharing*: results and application re-use and sharing within the community is a key aspect in the scientific analysis process towards Open Science. At the same time, sharing the analysis definition will result in an increased collaboration between different scientists and groups. Services supporting code and data sharing are, hence, another important part of the environment.

B. ENES Data Space Architecture

The ENES Data Space architecture has been defined starting from the aforementioned key objectives. Figure 1 shows a high-level view of the ENES Data Space architecture, highlighting the main infrastructural components considered. These include:

- a web-based GUI providing a data science environment where scientists can run their own applications, perform interactive data analysis and run analytics workflows. Software from project Jupyter is exploited to implement this layer;
- a pre-configured ecosystem of Python-based tools and frameworks for parallel data analysis and result visualization;
- a data access layer enabling users to access a set of ready-to-use datasets, but also to publish and share their experiments and results with other scientists and either public or closed communities;

³IPCC Reports: <https://www.ipcc.ch/reports/>

Fig. 1. High-level architecture of the ENES Data Space

- a state-of-the-art cloud-based infrastructure offering the scalable computing platform for data and compute-driven applications and services;
- a data collector and its local storage to gather the relevant datasets from ESGF and keep them synchronized with the remote repositories.
- an orthogonal AAI and monitoring layer to enable federated authentication and authorization of users, to deal with identity management and to access control aspects.

C. ENES Data Space Implementation

This section describes the main technologies used to implement the architecture layers presented in the previous subsection.

1) *Jupyter-based Data Science Interface*: The Data Science gateway to the ENES Data Space is implemented through *JupyterHub* [8], which is a server for running a multi-user Jupyter-based environment managing user authentication and authorization. AAI aspects are handled through the *EGI Check-in*⁴ service, directly integrated into *JupyterHub*. *EGI Check-in* provides users with a uniform, easy and secure way to access the service, also supporting authentication through institutional and social media accounts.

The *JupyterHub* server spawns single-user notebook servers with the enhanced *JupyterLab* [8] computing environment: the next-generation user interface for Project Jupyter. This environment contains a wide set of pre-configured scientific modules from the Python ecosystem targeting the climate community needs, such as *Xarray* [15], *Intake* [16], as well as computing frameworks like *Dask* [17] and *Ophidia* [18],

⁴EGI Check-in: <https://www.egi.eu/services/check-in/>

[19]). The whole Jupyter Notebook server and the Python ecosystem is implemented through a Docker container for easy deployment on the underlying cloud platform.

2) *Cloud-based computing platform*: The resources for the execution of the single-user container-based environment are provided by the EGI Federated Cloud e-Infrastructure⁵. Specifically, the *EC3 - Elastic Cloud Computing Cluster* service [20] is used to manage and elastically adapt the deployment of a Kubernetes cluster on top of the EGI resources. *EC3* combines the features of the *Infrastructure Manager (IM)* [21] with *CLUES* [22] features to provision and configure the resources, and to manage the cluster size. In this way, the resources assigned to the ENES Data Space dynamically grow and shrink according to the actual users' workload, measured, for example, in terms of memory usage, CPUs and number of pods in a node.

Kubernetes [23] is used to automate the deployment of the Docker-based micro-services and single-user environments of the ENES Data Space system. In this respect, *Kubernetes* allows managing the deployment of consistent and isolated environments for data scientists on top of the EGI Federated Cloud resources. Due to page limits, a more detailed description of this part is out of the scope of this paper and will be presented in a future work along with the set of containerized applications available in the ENES Data Space.

More specifically, the *JupyterHub Kubernetes Spawner* (also known as *KubeSpawner*)⁶ is in charge of spawning and

⁵The EGI Federated Cloud Infrastructure: <https://www.egi.eu/federation/egi-federated-cloud/>

⁶kubespawner documentation: <https://jupyterhub-kubespawner.readthedocs.io>

managing the user Docker containers that include the whole Python environment across the Kubernetes cluster nodes.

3) *Data Access and Sharing*: Each user is provided with a persistent dedicated storage space on the ENES Data Space file system, which is exposed to the various Kubernetes virtual machines composing the cluster and mapped into the user container at deployment time. This storage space can be used by scientists to store their notebooks and results between their experiment sessions in the ENES Data Space, prior to publication and sharing with other users. Moreover, each user environment has access to a large collection of ready-to-use datasets from the ESGF federated archive. The data collector is based on Synda [24], which allows datasets downloading and (one-way) synchronization of the local data pool with the data hosted on the ESGF data infrastructure. Results, output products and the experiment definitions (in the form of Jupyter Notebooks) can be easily shared among users through the data sharing services included in the environment, such as *Onedata* [25]. Moreover, Jupyter Notebooks can also be published and shared on GitHub and accessed within the data space thanks to the integration of the related JupyterLab extension.

IV. SCIENTIFIC APPLICATIONS SUPPORTED

The ENES Data Space enables various kinds of usages for data-centric research scenarios in the climate science domain, through a rich ecosystem of open source Python modules and community-based tools (e.g., intake, Ophidia, Xarray, Cartopy, etc.), supporting, for example, interactive analysis, parallel processing and workflows composed of several analytics tasks. Figure 2 shows a snapshot from the ENES Data Space portal portraying the gallery of example notebooks available to the users.

The following subsections describe some key aspects of the research workflow enabled by the proposed scientific gateway.

Fig. 2. Gallery of Jupyter Notebooks

1) *Data Search & Discovery*: The ENES Data Space is equipped with 150TB of storage capacity and provides access to a set of ready-to-use specific *CMIP* and *CORDEX* variable-centric collections from the ESGF federated data archive. Additional data can be integrated into the collection based on users’ needs, who can ask for new datasets by filling out a request form available on the data space portal. Synda will take care of retrieving the requested data and keeping the Data Space synchronized with the ESGF archive.

Before loading data and analyzing it, users need to understand which datasets are available, the metadata describing each dataset, and how they can select and access a specific dataset. In this regard, users can exploit the *intake-esm* data cataloging utility directly within a notebook in order to parse and execute queries against the Earth System Model catalog associated with the ENES Data Space archive, thus selecting in a simple way specific datasets from those available in the collection.

2) *Data Analysis & Visualization*: Once the data have been identified by querying the system, *intake-esm* can also be used to load data assets (i.e., NetCDF files), for example, into Xarray datasets. Alternately, scientists can exploit the Ophidia framework and its Python bindings, *PyOphidia*, to perform data analysis on multidimensional scientific datasets. These two solutions also allow parallel data processing.

The Data Science software stack also includes libraries to perform data visualization on the results of the analysis. In this regard, users can exploit the Xarray’s plotting capabilities to easily create informative plots. On top of this, they can use directly Matplotlib and Cartopy libraries to create customized and publication quality maps and geospatial visualizations.

Figure 3 shows a snapshot of a simple analysis and visualization workflow for climate sciences implemented in the form of Jupyter Notebook through the JupyterLab computing environment provided by the platform.

3) *Reusability & Sharing*: As introduced earlier, collaboration between research groups is key to future scientific discovery within an Open Science context. In this respect, the reuse of analysis workflows and the shareability of code and results are critical concepts. Jupyter Notebooks represent an easy way to create and share computational documents embedding code, explanation and results, thus encouraging code portability and reusability. This could also be a valuable aspect for training and education purposes in order to improve productivity through knowledge sharing and to address recurring learning difficulties.

In addition, through the integration with Onedata, the ENES Data Space offers users the possibility to publish and share their experiments and analysis results and to make them available to a specific community or worldwide across federated sites. On the same line, the definition of scientists’ experiments can also be shared through GitHub and accessed directly from the JupyterLab interface.

Fig. 3. A simple climate use case for data analysis and visualization

V. RELATED WORK

Several efforts can be found in literature about collaborative, web-based and easy-to-use platforms targeting data analytics at scale for eScience. Although each research group has addressed the requirements of their specific user community, some common aspects can be found in these works concerning: (i) the use of the data science environment based on *Project Jupyter* software components to enable interactive analysis and usable interfaces, (ii) and the integration of Python-based data science modules and frameworks (e.g., Dask) together with the computing infrastructure (both Cloud and HPC) providing users ready-to-use software environments for efficient data analysis.

Before diving into similar research efforts, it is important to mention one of the most well-known projects supporting eScience in the Python ecosystem: *Pangeo*. This is a community-based effort for the development of an open source software ecosystem for scalable big data analysis in geosciences [26]. The *Pangeo* environment consists of a set of core components, namely Xarray, Iris, Dask and Jupyter Notebooks and other related packages. The ENES Data Space builds on some of the solutions used by *Pangeo*.

As concerns the platforms for eScience whose deployment is close to big data archives, Juneau et al. [27] present two Jupyter-based science platforms designed to support the astronomy community in the analysis of large datasets. These platforms provide analysis and visualisation features close to large astronomical databases, and also enable a network of geographically distributed collaborators to access these resources. Another project [28] in the field of climate sciences presents the *Earth Data Analytics Services* (EDAS) framework, i.e., a HPDA and ML solution based on Xarray, Dask and other climate-domain tools, as well as ML tools (e.g., Keras and Tensorflow) and the Jupyter Notebook application. The framework aims to support climate scientists in running interactive and parallel analysis workflows close to the NASA massive data stores and on ESGF data. Similarly, Kanterakis et al. [29] propose a collaborative virtual research platform to support bioinformatics research. The environment provides scientists with a user-friendly access to integrated and inter-

operable resources, fostering multi-disciplinary collaboration among different research communities towards using the large amount of genomic and biomedical data currently available.

In several cases, the efforts have focused on providing researchers with simplified science gateways to computing resources, for example on HPC and Cloud infrastructures, through a usable interface for interactive (e.g., Jupyter Notebooks), scalable and reproducible computing [30]–[32].

The reviewed efforts show a general trend in the adoption of novel, user-friendly and GUI-based platforms, and also the importance for scientific research environments to fully support scalable and interactive scientific analysis, as well as to encourage a cultural shift towards more collaborative and reproducible research. The ENES Data Space environment proposed in this work, similarly to the efforts reviewed from literature, strives to provide users (i.e., climate sciences users) with a ready-to-use research environment through a web-based science gateway (i.e., Jupyter Notebooks) and cutting-edge modules and frameworks for data analytics and visualization (i.e., Python-based), closely integrated with the computing infrastructure and large scientific datasets.

However, with respect to these platforms, the ENES Data Space environment does not target users from a specific institution or group, but rather the broader climate community. This integrated environment thus allows scientists to be more productive on the one hand, since they do not need to install any tool or download big datasets locally, and, on the other hand, it allows supporting users who do not have access to computing infrastructures capable of supporting large-scale analysis. This can effectively democratize data analysis by providing opportunities to new user groups and communities.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the ENES Data Space, an EOSC-based data science environment for the climate community developed in the context of the EGI-ACE project.

The main motivations behind this data science environment have been introduced, together with the key requirements addressed, the software architecture devised to enable interactive and parallel data analysis/visualization, the supported scientific applications as well as the interactive gateway based on Jupyter Notebooks.

The environment was made accessible to end users in 2021, and it has been periodically updated with new software releases, datasets, and tools. This will continue as a natural extension of the data space, especially driven by the users' feedback and requests.

Finally, as emerged from the literature review, the integration of these data science environments with High Performance Computing infrastructures still represents an open challenge with respect to supporting large-scale, cloud-enabled analytics applications.

This is also an ongoing work for the ENES Data Space in the EGI-ACE project, where a piloting activity on this topic is being conducted to explore the available solutions, including assessing and identifying the most promising ones.

The production-level integration of such capabilities into a High Performance Computing environment represents future work for the ENES Data Space, which will enable transparent provisioning of containerized data analytics solutions through novel HPC as a Service (HPCaaS) paradigms.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the EGI-ACE project (Horizon 2020) under Grant number 101017567 and by the EU H2020 IS-ENES Phase 3 (ISENES3, Grant Agreement 824084). The authors would like to acknowledge Enol Fernández from EGI Foundation, Miguel Caballer from Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) and Hakan Bayindir from TUBİTAK ULAKBİM for their technical support. Moreover, the authors would like to acknowledge Antonio Aloisio from CMCC Foundation for his editing and proofreading work on this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Gregory, "The CF metadata standard," *CLIVAR Exchanges*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 4, 2003.
- [2] "Towards a common European data space - communication from the commission to the european parliament, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions," European Commission, Tech. Rep., 4 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0232>
- [3] "A European strategy for data - communication from the commission to the european parliament, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions," European Commission, Tech. Rep., 2 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0066&qid=1619802547376>
- [4] "Draft proposal for a European Partnership under Horizon Europe - European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership," European Commission, Tech. Rep., 5 2020. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he-partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf
- [5] European Commission and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, "Landscape of eoscc-related infrastructures and initiatives : report from the eoscc executive board working group (wg) landscape," 2020.
- [6] M. D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg *et al.*, "The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship," *Scientific data*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2016.
- [7] WCRP coupled model intercomparison project (CMIP). [Online]. Available: <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>
- [8] B. E. Granger and F. Pérez, "Jupyter: Thinking and storytelling with code and data," *Computing in Science Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 7–14, 2021.
- [9] J. Dongarra, P. Beckman, T. Moore *et al.*, "The international exascale software project roadmap," *The International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 3–60, 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342010391989>
- [10] J. L. Schnase, T. J. Lee, C. A. Mattmann *et al.*, "Big data challenges in climate science: Improving the next-generation cyberinfrastructure," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 10–22, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MGRS.2015.2514192>
- [11] L. Cinquini, D. Crichton *et al.*, "The earth system grid federation: An open infrastructure for access to distributed geospatial data," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 36, pp. 400–417, 2014.
- [12] Working group on coupled modelling. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-overview>
- [13] V. Balaji, K. E. Taylor, M. Juckes *et al.*, "Requirements for a global data infrastructure in support of CMIP6," *Geoscientific Model Development*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 3659–3680, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-3659-2018>
- [14] R. Petrie, S. Denvil, S. Ames *et al.*, "Coordinating an operational data distribution network for CMIP6 data," *Geoscientific Model Development*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 629–644, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-629-2021>
- [15] S. Hoyer and J. Hamman, "xarray: N-D labeled arrays and datasets in python," *Journal of Open Research Software*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.org/10.5334/jors.148>
- [16] , "Intake documentation," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://intake.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>
- [17] M. Rocklin, "Dask: Parallel computation with blocked algorithms and task scheduling," in *Proceedings of the 14th Python in Science Conference*, K. Huff and J. Bergstra, Eds. Austin, TX, USA: SciPy, 2015, pp. 130 – 136. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.25080/Majora-7b98e3ed-013>
- [18] S. Fiore, A. D'Anca, C. Palazzo *et al.*, "Ophidia: Toward big data analytics for eScience," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational Science, ICCS 2013, Barcelona, Spain, 5-7 June, 2013*, 2013, pp. 2376–2385. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2013.05.409>
- [19] D. Elia, S. Fiore, and G. Aloisio, "Towards HPC and big data analytics convergence: Design and experimental evaluation of a HPDA framework for eScience at scale," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 73 307–73 326, 2021.
- [20] M. Caballer, C. de Alfonso, F. Alvarruiz, and G. Moltó, "Ec3: Elastic cloud computing cluster," *Journal of Computer and System Sciences*, vol. 79, no. 8, pp. 1341–1351, 2013.
- [21] M. Caballer, I. Blanquer, G. Moltó, and C. de Alfonso, "Dynamic management of virtual infrastructures," *Journal of Grid Computing*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 53–70, 2015.
- [22] C. De Alfonso, M. Caballer, F. Alvarruiz, and V. Hernández, "An energy management system for cluster infrastructures," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 39, no. 8, pp. 2579–2590, 2013.
- [23] Kubernetes Documentation, "What is kubernetes?" 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/what-is-kubernetes/>
- [24] Data access and synchronization with synda. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.enes.org/data/metadata-service/data-discovery/synda>
- [25] Łukasz Dutka, M. Wrzeszcz, T. Lichoń *et al.*, "Onedata – a step forward towards globalization of data access for computing infrastructures," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 51, pp. 2843–2847, 2015, international Conference On Computational Science, ICCS 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050915012533>
- [26] J. Hamman, M. Rocklin, and R. Abernathy, "Pangeo: a big-data ecosystem for scalable earth system science," in *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts*, 2018, p. 12146.
- [27] S. Juneau, K. Olsen, R. Nikutta *et al.*, "Jupyter-enabled astrophysical analysis using data-proximate computing platforms," *Computing in Science Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 15–25, 2021.
- [28] T. P. Maxwell, D. Duffy, L. Carriere, and G. L. Potter, "The Earth Data Analytic Services (EDAS) Framework," in *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, vol. 2018, 12 2018, pp. IN53D–0649.
- [29] A. Kanterakis, N. Karacapilidis, L. Koumakis, and G. Potamias, "On the development of an open and collaborative bioinformatics research environment," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 126, pp. 1062 – 1071, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.08.043>
- [30] M. B. Milligan, "Jupyter as common technology platform for interactive HPC services," in *Proceedings of the Practice and Experience on Advanced Research Computing*, ser. PEARC '18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3219104.3219162>
- [31] D. Yin, Y. Liu, H. Hu *et al.*, "CyberGIS-Jupyter for reproducible and scalable geospatial analytics," *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, vol. 31, no. 11, p. e5040, 2019, e5040 cpe.5040. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.5040>
- [32] S. Cholia, L. Heagy, M. Henderson *et al.*, "Towards interactive, reproducible analytics at scale on HPC systems," in *2020 IEEE/ACM HPC for Urgent Decision Making (UrgentHPC)*, 2020, pp. 47–54. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/UrgentHPC51945.2020.00011>